

Analyzing Nonlinear Responses in a Tapered, Viscous Cochlear Model

Vipin Agarwal^{1, a)} and Karl Grosh^{2, 3, 4, b)}

¹*Department of Mechanical Engineering, The University of Memphis, 322A Engineering Science Building, Memphis, TN 38152, U.S.A.*

²*Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Michigan, G.G. Brown Building, 2350 Hayward St., Ann Arbor, MI 48109-2125, U.S.A*

³*Department of Biomedical Engineering, University of Michigan, 1107 Carl A. Gerstacker Building, 2200 Bonisteel, Blvd., Ann Arbor, MI 48109-2099, U.S.A.*

⁴*Kresge Hearing Research Institute, 4605 Medical Science Unit II, Ann Arbor, MI 48109-5616, U.S.A.*

^{a)}Corresponding author: vipin.a@memphis.edu

^{b)}grosh@umich.edu

Abstract. In this study, we develop a computational model to predict the mammalian cochlea's response to various sounds, integrating anatomical structures and electromechanical interactions. The model addresses challenges of varying length and time scales and complex physics involving diverse propagation speeds and viscous boundary layers. Using an alternating frequency-time fixed-point iteration approach, we analyze nonlinear responses of the cochlear model from base to apex under harmonic input. Our findings show nonlinear compression in the basilar membrane (BM) and hypercompression in the reticular lamina (RL), attributed to the interaction between nonlinear amplification and linear passive response. At higher sound levels, the active and passive effects partially cancel each other, leading to lower responses as sound pressure levels increase.

INTRODUCTION

In this paper, the nonlinear gain of the basilar membrane (BM) and reticular lamina (RL) in response to sound are studied. These two structures display dramatically different input-output characteristics over the auditory frequency range. The BM shows a narrow-band compressive nonlinearity centered around the characteristic frequency (CF) of the measurement location, while the RL nonlinearity is broad-band and can even produce a so-called hypercompressive nonlinearity (defined by a decrease in the amplitude of motion upon increasing input pressure). Using a mathematical model, we develop mechanistic descriptions as to how these difference response patterns arise from the same biomechanical system.

MODEL

To explore the multi-scale dynamics of the cochlea, we employ a combination of analytical and numerical methods to create a detailed model. This model depicts the cochlea as a prismatic box with two fluid-filled ducts connected at the apex (see Fig. 1(A)). The coordinates x , y , and z represent the longitudinal, radial, and transverse directions, respectively. We assume that the stapes and round window membranes interact with the fluid in the scala vestibuli (SV) and the scala tympani (ST). Additionally, the basilar membrane (BM) is centered along the radial direction throughout the cochlea. The organ of Corti (see Fig. 1(B)) is modeled as a composite structure comprising hair cells, pillar cells, hair bundles, and the tectorial membrane. The fluids in both scalae are coupled with the BM, while the organ of Corti is treated as acoustically transparent.

Building on this anatomical foundation, we use a 2.5-D hybrid finite element model of the guinea pig cochlea, which incorporates physiological parameters based on measurements in guinea pigs or similar mammals [1]. In this model, the BM is represented as an orthotropic plate, and the tectorial membrane is modeled as a longitudinally coupled viscoelastic beam [2]. The organ of Corti is treated as an electromechanical micro-system. Key features of the model include outer hair cell (OHC) electromotility driven by hair bundle (HB) rotation-induced conductance fluctuations, nonlinearity caused by mechano-electrical transduction (MET) saturation, viscous fluid-structure interaction throughout the cochlear ducts, and electrical conductivity through the three scalae.

The dynamics of this complex system are derived from a kinematically constrained, Lagrangian formulation. We use a finite element approach to solve the resulting governing partial differential equations (PDEs). These coupled

FIGURE 1. The schematic of the model of the cochlea. (A) The cochlea is modeled as two fluid ducts separated by the cochlear partition. The heights of the scala H_{SV} and H_{ST} change along with cytoarchitectural, and the width W is kept constant at 1 mm throughout the cochlea. (B) The kinematic structure of the organ of Corti is shown on the right. The directions of the displacement of the RL (u_{RL}) and the BM (u_{BM}) are shown with red and blue arrows, respectively.

PDEs are expressed in the frequency domain as

$$(-M\omega^2 - i\omega C + K) \mathbf{X}(\omega) + \mathcal{F}[\mathbf{NL}(t)] = \mathbf{F}(\omega) \quad , \quad (1)$$

where the matrices \mathbf{M} , \mathbf{C} , and \mathbf{K} represent the mass, damping, and stiffness, respectively, and \mathbf{X} is the solution vector. The term \mathbf{NL} contains the nonlinear mapping of the forcing from the MET current to the rest of the system, and \mathcal{F} denotes the Fourier transform, which extracts the force at the solution frequency. Finally, \mathbf{F} contains the linear forcing terms. The multi-frequency nonlinear solution \mathbf{X} is calculated iteratively using the alternate time-frequency method [3]. This comprehensive approach allows us to capture the intricate dynamics of the cochlea, providing insights into its function and response to various stimuli.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Our analysis covers nonlinear models with varying frequencies and stimulus levels, ranging from 6kHz to 25kHz, and 10 dB SPL to 90 dB SPL, respectively. We derive frequency-response curves for both the basilar membrane (BM) and reticular lamina (RL) at various locations, observing nonlinear compression at different stimulus levels, as shown in Fig. 2. The results are in harmony with the experimental observations [4, 5].

In accordance with experimental data [6, 7], we find that the RL exhibits hypercompression rather than the compressive behavior seen in the BM response at the base of the cochlea, as shown in Fig. 3.

We find that this compressive behavior is due to the interaction of the strongly nonlinear amplification arising from the active process and the linear forcing due to the passive response to acoustic stimulus. For the BM, active and passive responses occur nearly in phase, and the overall response presents as a saturating nonlinearity. Conversely, at the RL, the active response, which is nonlinear and saturates, is not synchronized with the linear response. The linear response of the RL is defined as its reaction to acoustic stimuli under passive conditions. At higher sound stimulus levels the two effects tend to partially cancel, giving rise to lower responses at increasing sound pressure levels in the region when the two effects are commensurate in level.

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FIGURE 2. Predicted gain functions. Gain curves at the 9 kHz place in our model with stimulation from 10-90 dB SPL. The BM (A) gain is seen to be linear (no compression) at low frequencies and highly compressive near CF (9 kHz). The RL gain (B) is compressive over all frequencies. The corresponding phase for the BM is shown in (C) and that for the RL is shown in (D). Both gain and phase are normalized with respect to stapes displacement.

FIGURE 3. Predicted Input output growth curve for the RL. Using our model, we predicted the I/O growth curve at frequency $f_0 = 18$ kHz at the 12 kHz best place are shown on the left. Higher SPL stimulus is seen to return to a monotonic increase in the RL displacement after a hypercompressive dip.

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COMMENTS AND DISCUSSION

[Lauren Chiriboga]: How does the longitudinal coupling of the TM influence the model? I assume it influences the HB motion. You examine frequencies between 6 - 25 kHz. Can this model go to higher frequencies? Would any of the parameters have to change as a result? I think including an I/O curve for the BM with the RL in Figure 3 would be a nice comparison. I see how the passive RL response is linear, but there also seems to be some linearity at the lowest SPL at the lowest frequencies. Is there an explanation for this? **Response:** The longitudinal coupling of the tectorial membrane plays a key role in influencing hair bundle motion and the resulting nonlinearity in the model. While the model could be extended to higher frequencies (>25 kHz), it is specifically designed to capture the hypercompression observed as presented here. Including an I/O curve for the basilar membrane alongside the RL would indeed be insightful, but it would not change the outcome of this study, and we plan to include this in a future full-length paper in future. The linearity at low SPL and frequencies is due to the predominance of passive cochlear mechanics in those scenarios.

[Anvy Kuriakose]: Why did you explore this multi-scale dynamics of cochlea, how is this model helping you study the responses of BM and RL? Could you point to what software/language you used to model this? What would be a practical implication of this lower response at increasing sound pressure levels? **Response:** We explored the multi-scale dynamics of the cochlea to accurately capture the complex interactions within its structures, particularly the basilar membrane (BM) and reticular lamina (RL). This modeling approach helps us understand the distinct responses of these structures, with the BM showing nonlinear compression and the RL exhibiting hypercompression. The hybrid finite element model, likely implemented in MATLAB, was used to simulate these dynamics. The observed lower response at higher sound pressure levels suggests a natural protective mechanism in the cochlea, which could inform the design of hearing aids and implants to prevent hearing damage.